

Development of Problem Solving-Based Student Worksheets to Improve Students' Science Process Skills on Reaction Rate Material

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ABSTRACT: The development of the education system encourages curriculum updates in Indonesia, one of which is through the implementation of the Merdeka Curriculum which emphasizes strengthening 21st century skills, including science process skills. Reaction rate material in chemistry subjects is abstract and requires an experimental approach to support concept understanding. This study aims to develop a problem solving-based Learner Worksheet that is feasible to use in improving students' science process skills on reaction rate material. The research method used is Research and Development (R&D) with the 4D model (Define, Design, Develop, Disseminate), limited to the Develop stage. The limited trial was conducted on 30 students of class XI SMA IPIEMS Surabaya. The instruments used included review sheets, expert validation, learner response questionnaires, activity observations, and science process skills tests (pretest and posttest). The validation results show that the LKPD has a high level of validity in the aspects of content, language, presentation, and graphics. Students' responses to the LKPD were very positive with an average score of 98%, which indicated the practicality of the Worksheet. The effectiveness of LKPD is also supported by an increase in science process skills scores based on pretest and posttest results. The effectiveness of LKPD is also supported by an increase in science process skills scores based on pretest and posttest results.

KEYWORDS: LKPD, problem solving, science process skills, reaction rate, 4D development

INTRODUCTION

The development of education in the 21st century has driven various transformations in education systems around the world, including in Indonesia. One of the major changes that occurred was the implementation of the Merdeka Curriculum, which is a curriculum designed to answer global challenges by emphasizing the strengthening of 21st century skills such as critical thinking, creativity, communication, collaboration, and problem solving [1]. This curriculum demands a learner-centered learning process, based on real-life contexts, and emphasizes mastery of science literacy and science process skills through active learning activities [2]. Science process skills are a set of intellectual and practical skills used in conducting scientific investigations. These skills include the ability to observe, formulate hypotheses, design and conduct experiments, analyze data, and draw conclusions [3]. These skills are not only important for understanding science material, but also play a role in shaping scientific thinking and the ability to solve problems systematically. In the Merdeka Curriculum, science process skills are one of the essential competencies that must be trained to students through inquiry-based learning and problem solving [4].

One of the chemistry materials that requires the application of science process skills is the reaction rate, especially the submaterial of factors that affect the reaction rate. This material has abstract characteristics and is difficult to understand without an experimental approach or direct observation of chemical phenomena [5]. Learners often have difficulty in connecting theoretical concepts with everyday events, resulting in low conceptual understanding. Therefore, a learning approach is needed that is able to bridge concepts with the reality of students' lives [6]. [7]

However, the results of pre-research conducted at Senior High School IPIEMS Surabaya show that the science process skills of students are still low. Of the 35 students studied, only 52.50% were able to formulate problems, 42% formulated hypotheses, 21.67% identified variables, and less than 31% could analyze data and draw conclusions correctly. The results of interviews with chemistry teachers also indicate that practicum activities are rarely carried out, and the learning process is still teacher-centered, which does not support the development of scientific thinking skills.

To overcome these problems, a learning model that encourages students to actively solve problems through a scientific approach is needed. The problem solving learning model is one approach that emphasizes the stages of understanding the problem, designing a solution, implementing the plan, and evaluating the results [8]. Based on Polya's four-step approach, learners are trained to identify

problems, develop hypotheses, design and conduct investigations, and critically evaluate their findings [9]. This approach encourages learners to learn independently, think logically, and link new knowledge with existing knowledge [10]. In order for the problem solving model to be applied effectively, learning media is needed that can guide students through each stage of learning. Learner Worksheet is one of the media that can be used to support this approach. Worksheet contains learning activity guides, problem scenarios, experimental procedures, and reflective questions designed to stimulate active involvement and development of students' science process skills [11]. If arranged based on the syntax of the problem solving model, Worksheet can train learners to think scientifically and solve problems related to everyday life [12].

Various previous studies have proven the effectiveness of problem solving-based Worksheet in improving science learning outcomes [13]. The use of Worksheet is also proven to increase learning motivation, encourage active learning, and create a fun and meaningful learning atmosphere [14]. Therefore, the development of Worksheet needs to be adjusted to the national curriculum standards and assessed based on three main aspects, namely validity, practicality, and effectiveness [15]. Based on this background, this study aims to develop a problem solving-based Learner Worksheet that is feasible to use to improve the science process skills of grade XI students on the material of factors that affect the reaction rate. The feasibility of the product is assessed based on aspects of validity, practicality, and effective.

METHOD

This research uses the Research and Development (R&D) method proposed by Thiagarajan and has four stages, known as the 4D model, namely define, design, develop, and disseminate [16]. This research is limited to the develop stage only, namely by conducting a limited trial of the Worksheet products that have been developed. The subjects of this study were 30 students of class XI-2 SMA IPIEMS Surabaya who had received material on factors that affect the rate of chemical reactions. The product developed in the form of problem solving-based Learner Worksheets, which aims to train students' science process skills through active and structured learning activities. The instruments used in this study consisted of: validation sheet to assess the validity of Worksheet; learner response questionnaire sheet and learner activity observation sheet to determine the level of practicality; and pretest and posttest sheets to measure the effectiveness of Worksheet in improving the science process skills of learners.

Before the learning process begins, students are given pretest questions about science process skills. Then learning was carried out using problem solving-based Worksheet for four meetings. After the learning activities are completed, students are given posttest questions that are equivalent to the pretest to measure the improvement of science process skills. The pretest and posttest questions were arranged based on four contextual phenomena designed to measure seven indicators of science process skills, namely: (1) formulating problems, (2) formulating hypotheses, (3) identifying variables, (4) designing experiments, (5) collecting data, (6) analyzing data, and (7) drawing conclusions. Data were analyzed using several techniques. Data from the validation sheet was analyzed using a Likert scale, while the student response questionnaire was analyzed using a Guttman scale. Furthermore, data from pretest and posttest results were analyzed using the Paired Sample t-Test test to determine statistically significant improvements.

Validation results are declared valid if they obtain a mode with a value of 3 (valid category) or 4 (very valid), as in Table 1.

Table 1. Category of Validity

<i>Value/Score</i>	<i>Category</i>
0	Very Invalid
1	Invalid
2	Fairly Valid
3	Valid
4	Very Valid

Source: Riduwan, 2015 [17]

furthermore, a student e-worksheet is declared practical if it obtains a practicality score percentage of $\geq 61\%$ in the very practicality category, as in Table 2. These results are also supported by the student activity observation sheet.

Table 2. Category of Practicality

<i>Percentage (%)</i>	<i>Category</i>
0 - 20	Impractical
21 - 40	Less Practical
41 - 60	Quite Practical
61 - 80	Practical
81 - 100	Very Practical

Source: Riduwan, 2015

Apart from that, the pretest-posttest results were analyzed using SPSS, including testing the normality of the data using the Shapiro Wilk normality test. The data is normal if it obtains a significance value of > 0.05 . After the data was declared normal, it was subjected to a paired sample t-test. The student e-worksheet being developed is declared effective if it obtains paired sample t-test results of < 0.05 [18].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This research applied the stages in the 4D development model proposed by Thiagarajan, namely Define, Design, Develop, and Disseminate. However, this research was only conducted up to the Develop stage.

A. Define

This stage consists of five analysis steps, namely initial and final analysis, student analysis, task analysis, concept analysis, and learning objectives analysis [19]. This initial and final analysis includes analyzing the curriculum used, namely the Merdeka Curriculum, which includes one subject, namely chemistry. One of the materials in chemistry is the factors that affect the rate of chemical reactions, which based on its characteristics can be applied using a problem solving-based learning model. This learning requires appropriate learning media, such as student worksheets. At the student analysis stage, an analysis of cognitive development and science process skills is carried out, the results of which show that students have cognitive development at the formal operational stage (aged 16-18 years) so that they can already think abstractly [20]. Students' science process skills are still relatively low based on the results of pre-research conducted. The concept analysis will produce a concept map of the material on factors that affect the rate of chemical reactions which will later be presented in the worksheet. Task analysis aims to determine the activities in the worksheet that will be completed by students as a place to train and improve science process skills. And finally, in the analysis of learning objectives, learning objectives and the flow of learning objectives are formulated which are adjusted to the achievement of chemistry learning in phase F of the Merdeka Curriculum.

B. Design

The design stage includes four main steps. First, compiling science process skills test questions based on seven indicators, namely: formulate problems, formulate hypotheses, identify variables, design experiments, collect data, analyze data, and draw conclusions. Second, the learning media chosen was worksheet in printed format. Third, the structure of the worksheet is organized into five parts, namely one main Worksheet and four worksheet based on factors that affect the reaction rate, namely concentration, surface area, temperature, and catalyst. Each worksheet contains identity, instructions for use, learning objectives, a series of problem solving-based activities, and reflective questions designed to train science process skills. Fourth, the worksheet draft was designed using the Canva application and saved in PDF format. The main cover can be seen in figure 1.

Figure 1. Cover Appearance of the Problem-Solving-Based Student Worksheet

C. Develop

At the develop stage, the initial draft of the worksheet was validated by two expert lecturers in chemistry education and one chemistry teacher. After validation, a limited trial was conducted with 30 students of class XI-2 SMA IPIEMS Surabaya for four meetings. During learning, students used problem solving-based worksheet to improve the factors that affect the reaction rate. The data collected included student response questionnaires, activity observation sheets, and pretest and posttest results.

D. Validity

Based on the validity data obtained, it can be seen that the results of the validation of student worksheets developed in terms of content validation include 13 aspects of assessment that obtain mode 3 with valid categories, and construct validity consists of 3 criteria, namely (1) language criteria include 3 aspects of assessment that obtain mode 3 with valid categories; (2) presentation criteria include 5 aspects of assessment with mode 3 with valid categories; and (3) graphical criteria include 4 aspects of assessment that obtain mode 3 with valid categories [21]. Overall, the student worksheets developed were declared very valid because they obtained mode 3 for content and construct validity.

E. Practicality

The practicality of the worksheet is known from the results of the learner response questionnaire which is supported by the student activity observation sheet during the learning process using worksheet in class. The response of students is their response or assessment of the problem solving-based worksheet given through a questionnaire sheet. Previous research states that problem solving-based worksheet is classified as practical for use in learning [22]. Riduwan stated that learning media is said to be practical if it gets a percentage $\geq 61\%$ based on the Guttman scale [21]. Based on the data from the trial results, it was found that the percentage of the results of the student response questionnaire was 98%, which was included in the very practical category. These results are reinforced by the results of observations of learner activities that show active involvement during learning activities. The activity of each learner in the group was observed by the observer for four meetings. The purpose of this observation is to determine the suitability of student activities with the stages or syntax of the problem solving learning model. Activities observed included: (1) students identify problems and gather information from the phenomena presented (phase 1 problem solving: understanding the problem), (2) students formulate problems based on the phenomena on the LKPD (phase 2: planning the solution), (3) students formulate hypotheses based on the information obtained (phase 2: planning the solution), (4) students process the data from the

activity and analyze the data to solve the problem (phase 3: implementing the plan), (5) students draw conclusions based on the results of the experiment and the phenomenon presented (phase 4: checking back), and (6) students reflect on the correctness of the solution that has been given (phase 4: checking back). The observation results show that the activities of students while using the worksheet are in accordance with the stages in the problem solving model and support the targeted science process skills. Thus, the developed worksheet is declared very practical to use in learning.

Figure 2. Process of Learning Activities in Class

Figure 3. Students carry out experiments based on the problem-solving-based student worksheet

F. Effectiveness

The effectiveness of student worksheets is known from the pretest-posttest results of science process skills on the material of factors that affect the rate of chemical reactions. This test consists of 7 description questions that contain 7 indicators of science process skills, namely formulating problems, formulating hypotheses, identifying variables, designing experiments, collecting data, analyzing and making conclusions [23]. The pretest was conducted before learning using the learner worksheet, and the posttest was conducted after learning using the learner worksheet, then the improvement was observed. The results of the data obtained are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Pretest and Posttest Results Data

Based on Figure 4, it can be seen that initially, students obtained low pretest scores in science process skills. However, after the implementation of learning using problem-solving-based worksheet on the topic of factors affecting the reaction rate, students' posttest scores showed a significant increase. This indicates an improvement in students' science process skills following the learning process using worksheet. These findings are in line with previous research which stated that problem-solving-based worksheet can effectively enhance students' science process skills [24].

The pretest and posttest data were then analyzed using SPSS, starting with the Shapiro-Wilk normality test. If the data were found to be normally distributed, the analysis was continued using a paired sample t-test. The results of the normality test for students' science process skills pretest and posttest can be seen in Figure 5.

Tests of Normality

	Kolmogorov-Smirnova			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistics	df	Sig.	Statistics	df	Sig.
Pretest	.159	30	.051	.939	30	.085
Posttest	.195	30	.005	.934	30	.063

Figure 5. Test of Normality

The test results showed a significance value of 0.085 for the pretest and 0.063 for the posttest, both of which are greater than 0.05, indicating that the data are normally distributed. Since the data met the normality assumption, the analysis was continued using a paired sample t-test. The results of the paired sample t-test for students' science process skills pretest and posttest can be seen in Figure 6.

Paired Samples Test

	Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
Pair 1 Pretest – Posttest	-47.967	5.980	1.092	-50.200	-45.734	-43.936	29	.000

Figure 6. Paired Sample t-test

Based on the results of the paired sample t-test, a significance value of 0.000 was obtained. Since this value is less than 0.05, it can be concluded that there is a significant difference between students' pretest and posttest scores in science process skills. Therefore,

the problem-solving-based worksheet developed in this study is considered effective in improving students' science process skills. This result is in line with the study conducted by Rahmawati & Yonata [25], which stated that problem-solving-based learning tools are effective in training students' science process skills through exploratory and structured learning activities. The improvement in students' science process skills occurred because the learning process using worksheet was carried out systematically, following the stages of Polya's problem-solving model: understanding the problem, devising a plan, carrying out the plan, and reviewing the results. Each stage was designed to train specific indicators of science process skills. In the first stage (understanding the problem), students were directed to observe phenomena, formulate problems, and identify relevant variables. In the next stage (planning), students developed hypotheses and designed steps for the experiment. The implementation stage encouraged students to conduct experiments according to the plan and collect the resulting data. Finally, students analyzed the data and drew logical conclusions based on their observations. The worksheet used in this study was designed based on contextual problems related to factors affecting reaction rates, such as concentration, temperature, surface area, and catalysts. This made the learning process more meaningful and helped students connect the concepts they learned with real-life phenomena. Supatmi [26] emphasized that science process skills can develop optimally when students are involved in experimental and investigative activities that challenge their scientific thinking abilities. In addition, each activity in the worksheet was designed to enable students to comprehensively develop their science process skills. The seven trained indicators—formulating problems, constructing hypotheses, identifying variables, designing experiments, collecting data, analyzing data, and drawing conclusions were consistently integrated into every activity in the worksheet. Students' active involvement in problem-solving encouraged them to think critically, work collaboratively, and build a deeper conceptual understanding. The findings of this study reinforce the growing body of evidence that problem-solving-based learning media can significantly improve students' thinking skills. Similar results were reported in previous studies, where the use of problem-solving-oriented worksheets or e-modules led to improvements not only in science process skills but also in creative and critical thinking abilities [27]. In particular, Cahyani found that problem-solving-oriented worksheets were able to train creative thinking skills effectively, achieving high N-Gain scores across all indicators of creativity, including fluency, flexibility, originality, and elaboration [28]. Moreover, the implementation of the problem-solving model in higher education settings has also shown to be effective. Azizah and Nasrudin [7] demonstrated that students' problem-solving thinking skills improved across all indicators, especially in applying plans and drawing conclusions, confirming the broader applicability of Polya's four-step model in chemistry learning. Based on statistical test results and the analysis of the learning process, it can be concluded that the problem-solving-based worksheet developed in this study is effective for improving the science process skills of eleventh-grade students in the topic of factors affecting the rate of chemical reactions. The learning becomes more meaningful, challenging, and aligned with 21st-century skill demands, particularly in terms of problem-solving and scientific thinking abilities.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research that has been conducted, it can be concluded that the problem-solving-based Student Worksheet on the topic of factors affecting the rate of chemical reactions is feasible to be used to improve the science process skills of eleventh-grade students, as assessed from the aspects of validity, practicality, and effectiveness. The validity of the worksheet is proven through expert validation results on content and construct aspects, which include language, presentation, and graphics, with a mode score of ≥ 3 , categorized as valid. The practicality of the worksheet is shown by the results of the student response questionnaire, which obtained a percentage of 98% (very practical category), and is supported by observations of student activities during the learning process. Meanwhile, the effectiveness of the worksheet is evidenced by the improvement in students' science process skills, which was analyzed using a paired sample t-test and yielded a significance value of 0.000 ($p < 0.05$), indicating a significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores. Thus, the developed problem-solving-based worksheet is proven to be valid, practical, and effective in enhancing students' science process skills.

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